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A Scalable Data-Driven Methodology for Human Intention Prediction in Diverse Collaborative Scenarios

Samuele Dell’Oca^{*1}, Elias Montini^{1,2}, Vincenzo Cutrona¹, Davide Matteri¹, Giuseppe Landolfi¹,
and Andrea Bettoni¹

Abstract— Collaborative robots were designed to work alongside humans and enable Human-Robot Collaboration in industry, but without intelligence, these robots cannot adapt, make decisions, or respond dynamically to human actions. They function more as programmable tools rather than true teammates. This study proposes a methodology to predict operators’ short-term intentions in various manufacturing scenarios. This predictive capability is integrated into an orchestration system, allowing the cobot to complement human actions and optimize task execution. The system identifies execution patterns and contextual features while incorporating predictions into a task assignment logic. Its key strength lies in its task-agnostic nature, enabling adaptation across different scenarios through a structured formalization of use-case characteristics. This flexibility allows reconfiguration to optimize performance in various industrial applications. The Intention Prediction Model was first validated in individual scenarios, demonstrating its ability to interpret human intentions in different manufacturing contexts. It was then tested with 12 participants in three collaborative scenarios, showing effective task adaptation, improved role synchronization, and task variability management, despite lower intention prediction accuracy compared to individual setups. While no collisions occurred, collaboration smoothness varied, indicating the need for advanced coordination techniques based on human intention interpretation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC) has advanced significantly in recent years, driven by the demand for more flexible, adaptive and easy-to-use automation systems [1]. As part of the broader push towards Industry 5.0, collaborative robots (cobots) have been introduced to work alongside human operators, especially in manufacturing environments [2]. Despite these advancements, cobots are still predominantly confined to highly structured tasks and lack the cognitive ability to understand or adapt to human intentions [3]. This limitation significantly impairs their effectiveness in dynamic, unstructured environments such as those found in smart production lines [4].

State-of-the-art research in HRC has focused heavily on task assignment models and static features in collaborative environments. Researchers have developed systems that allow cobots to assist human operators by performing complementary tasks in manufacturing settings [5]. However,

current models are primarily reactive rather than proactive and limited to specific scenarios [6], as they rely on direct input from operators (via interfaces or sensors) or rigidly defined task sequences.

A significant limitation of cobot is their restricted intelligence, in fact they are intrinsically designed for collaboration (e.g., inability to harm) but often struggle to adapt to varied collaborative tasks. This limitation is evident in their lack of flexibility and adaptive behavior, particularly when responding to diverse human partners. For instance, they face challenges anticipating and adjusting to various human behaviors and real-time errors [7]. Another key limitation of cobots is their lack of context-awareness, which hinders their ability to adapt to changes and ensure efficient collaboration in dynamic environments. Moreover, they typically follow pre-programmed instructions (e.g., to perform screwing operations on a predefined set of screws in a specific order), leading to inefficiencies in human-robot interactions. These issues manifest in lower task performance, increased errors and reduced operator trust due to the cobots’ inability to adapt dynamically to human actions [8].

To address these challenges, this research proposes a generalized intention prediction methodology to support proactive cobot adaptation [9], where actions are adjusted based on predicted human intentions (intended as a finite set of short-term actions). The methodology enables an orchestration system to dynamically interpret intentions across manufacturing scenarios, optimizing task assignment to complement human actions effectively. The system balances human control—allowing natural movement—while leveraging robotic assistance to reduce effort [10]. Although tasks are not explicitly assigned to the human, their actions are influenced by the cobot’s movements and tasks. This balance enables the operator to work freely while benefiting from reduced physical and cognitive effort, as the cobot both lessens task load and supports strategic decision-making.

This approach enables the improvement of task fluidity, coordination and human-cobot trust. It represents a shift towards collaborative automation, synchronizing human and robot to optimize performance and worker satisfaction. In addition, the intention prediction methodology is versatile, designed to be consistent in various use cases, requiring only minimal customization to fit diverse scenarios: this is what makes the approach scalable, in contrast to traditional systems tailored to a single use case, which often results in significant waste of resources, such as time, money, and development effort.

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Starting from a state-of-the-art analysis in Section II, the methodology is formalized in Section III. Section IV details the experiments to validate the model and the orchestration system in three scenarios. Validation results are discussed in Section V, while achievements and limitations are finally presented in Section VI.

II. STATE OF THE ART

Recent studies have explored cobots and Artificial Intelligence (AI) to enhance HRC by predicting human intentions, improving efficiency and coordination. Most existing approaches focus on a single use case, primarily predicting human motion trajectories.

Early methods employed Probabilistic State Machines (PSMs) for classifying explicit and implicit intention communication across different scenarios [11], or Markov Decision Processes (MDPs) for predicting intention and support decision-making in shared workspaces [12]. Later approaches introduced Deep Learning (DL) models leveraging visual signals for disassembly [13], and Gaussian Mixture Models for assembly [14]. More recently, recurrent neural models (e.g., Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) and bi-directional LSTM) have been preferred for their ability to capture temporal dependencies, improving prediction accuracy and robot adaptation [15], including also Convolutional LSTM for action anticipation based on spatio-temporal features [16]. Transformer-based models are also emerging for early intention prediction, enabling proactive robot assistance and reducing response times [17]. In complex industrial settings, multimodal Machine Learning (ML) using multiple data sources (video, audio, haptic) has enhanced intention recognition accuracy [18].

Multitask learning frameworks, such as LSTM-based models predicting multilevel human intention across six assembly tasks [19], have been proposed, but validations remain tailored to single activities. This does not reflect the variability of manufacturing environments, which include assembly, disassembly, picking, and decision-making. Addressing this requires adaptable systems capable of handling multiple scenarios, a current research gap. Table I highlights literature trends in interpreting human intentions to adapt robot actions across diverse contexts using common model structures.

TABLE I: Overview of existing approaches to human intention prediction in HRC literature.

Paper	Model	Task agnostic	Validation scenarios (number of scenarios)
[11]	PSM	Yes	Pick & place task (1)
[12]	MDP	No	Intra-vehicle activity (1)
[13]	DL	No	Disassembly task (1)
[14]	GMM	No	Assembly task (1)
[15]	IBi-LSTM	No	Assembly task (1)
[16]	ConvLSTM	No	Assembly task (1)
[17]	Transformer	No	HRC task (1)
[18]	Multimodal ML	No	Assembly task (1)
[19]	LSTM	Yes	Assembly task (1)
[20]	DL + attention	Yes	Object handover, harvesting (2)
[21]	Self-superv. ML	Yes	Social tasks (3)

Latest advances incorporate DL architectures with attention mechanisms for predicting human motion in different collaborative tasks [20]. Additionally, self-supervised learning has shown promising results in predicting user interactions with service robots in dynamic environments [21].

III. METHODOLOGY

The proposed approach involves the development of a generalized human Intention Prediction Model (IPM) to predict human tasks in manufacturing processes with the ultimate goal to support HRC in diverse applications.

The scenario involves a human operator H , who operates within a discrete state environment, where each state corresponds to a specific configuration. This discrete state formalization is a foundational constraint that enables flexibility in other aspects of the system's design. The scenario configuration $Conf$ is represented as a binary matrix $N \times M$, where N denotes the number of elements defining a scenario, and M represents the possible states that these elements can assume (i.e., the locations where they can be placed). For instance, $Conf_{n,m} = 1$ indicates that the n -th element is currently assigned to m -th location.

$$Conf = \begin{bmatrix} Conf_{1,1} & Conf_{1,2} & \dots & Conf_{1,M} \\ Conf_{2,1} & Conf_{n,m} & \dots & Conf_{2,M} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ Conf_{N,1} & Conf_{N,2} & \dots & Conf_{N,M} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$Conf_{n,m} \in \{0, 1\}$$

For every scenario, a finite set of tasks I is defined, each represented as a linear independent vector i . A task $i \in I$ is intended as a sequence of actions required to achieve a goal. Note that in some cases, e.g., if an element n is targeted by multiple tasks i , then $|N| \neq |I|$.

A function $T : Conf \times I \rightarrow Conf$ is defined to represent the execution of a task with a given configuration. Starting from a configuration at time t ($Conf_t$), the next configuration $Conf_{t+1}$ is obtained as:

$$Conf_{t+1} = T(Conf_t, i), i \in I$$

The application of different sequences of tasks might result in the same final configuration $Conf$, and some tasks are reversible. A task execution T is considered complete when the expected conditions associated with its outcome are met, regardless of which actions are taken, as these can vary from person to person.

Depending on the scenario, every human H decides autonomously which task i to perform at each instant t , based on subjective (hidden) decisional criteria. A smart orchestration system needs to discover the hidden knowledge to manage the task assignments for other entities involved in the scenario (e.g., a cobot). In fact, the system is able to determine i in case H is already performing the task, otherwise it needs to decide it.

A. Intention Prediction Model

The goal of the IPM is to predict the task i that a human H is more likely to execute at time $t+1$ based on the current $Conf_t$ and features that characterize the preferences and behaviour of human H at time t . Such features are classified into three main categories:

- *Context-related*: representing the scenario configuration, it corresponds to flattened $Conf$ at a specific instant t .
- *Dynamic human-related*: capturing real-time data on human movement, including the position or status of specific body parts.
- *Static human-related*: encompassing operator-specific attributes such as experience, skills, and preferences.

Human-related features are concatenated into a unidimensional vector V , which, together with $Conf$, serves as the input of the model to predict the next task i .

More formally, the hidden human decision function can be defined as follows:

$$F(Conf_t, V_t) = i$$

Consequently, the IPM learns a function M such that:

$$M(Conf_t, V_t) = \bar{i} \approx i$$

where \bar{i} is an approximation of i . Finally, \bar{i} is matched to a task $i \in I$ denoted as i^* , accordingly to a scoring function G . i^* is the output of the IPM:

$$i^* = \underset{i \in I}{\operatorname{argmax}} G(i, \bar{i})$$

The modular structure enables easy extension and customization of the IPM to fit diverse applications. For instance, additional features can be incorporated into V depending on the use case, such as detailed monitoring of the operator’s face, hands, or arms, as well as scenario-specific required skills or preferences. All models maintain a consistent feature structure despite these customizations, as detailed in Table II.

A key characteristic of this model is its ability to learn patterns from task sequences by focusing on the semantic meaning of configurations rather than calculating vector distances, avoiding misleading similarities between numerically close but contextually different states. Moreover, it replicates historical sequences and generates new ones by considering the current task sequence and dynamic human features. This adaptability allows the model to respond to real-time human actions and environmental changes, enhancing its flexibility.

TABLE II: Overview of the models’ feature set

Parameter	Description	Example
$Conf(t)$	It represents the scenario configuration (i.e., its elements status)	[1,0,1,1,0]
P_{eyes}	Position of the center between the eyes [x, y]	[317,127]
P_{nose}	Position of the nose tip [x, y]	[315,138]
P_{right}	Position of the right hand [x, y]	[378,243]
P_{left}	Position of the left hand [x, y]	[484,138]
D	Operator dominant hand (right=1, left=0)	1

Additionally, the model autonomously learns constraints and dependencies from training data without explicit rule formulation. By analyzing valid task sequences, it predicts actions based on learned patterns, enhancing flexibility and eliminating manual rule definitions. For example, the model would not be explicitly instructed on the rules of a game or the constraints of a procedure. It learns these constraints through training, demonstrating the effectiveness of properly formalizing and discretizing the scenario.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

The experimental phase involved developing three scenarios, each with a tailored version of IPM designed to leverage context-related features relevant to the specific operational scenario, along with the associated orchestration system.

These scenarios closely reflect real manufacturing applications: Piece disassembly, depicted in Fig. 1a, mirrors industrial tasks like remanufacturing or recycling, where workers and robots work in dismantling complex products. LEGO® assembly, displayed in Fig. 1b, represents structured, repeatable assembly tasks, similar to manual and robotic workstations assembling components with precision. The Tower of Hanoi, shown in Fig. 1c, exemplifies sequential problem-solving in constrained environments, such as rearranging workpieces based on dependencies, and tests cooperative strategy execution.

According to the methodology presented in Section III, the scenarios have been discretized, leading to different structure and meaning of $Conf_{n,m}$, as detailed in Table III.

TABLE III: Overview of scenarios configurations

Scenario	$Conf$ ($N \times M$)	Meaning of 0	Meaning of 1
Piece disassembly	15×1	Screw n has been removed	Screw n is present on the piece
LEGO® assembly	14×1	Piece n has been collected	Piece n is still in the warehouse
Tower-of Hanoi	5×3	Disk n is absent on rod m	Disk n is present on rod m

For each scenario, a Deep Neural Network has been defined, building on the architecture introduced in [?] and changing the input and output layers to match the shapes of $Conf$ and V . To train the networks, a dataset has been built by defining individual scenarios where a human was in charge of completing all the tasks. Each individual scenario involved three participants, with different expertise levels in completing the tasks (newbie, regular, expert). Each participant completed a fixed amount of rounds per scenario, depending on the scenario complexity: 5 rounds for Piece disassembly, 10 for LEGO® assembly, and 3 for Tower of Hanoi. The obtained datasets contain 7.5k, 20k, and 12k rows, respectively. After preprocessing for encoding and normalization, they were split into 80% for training and 20% for testing, with 20% of the test set reserved for model validation. The trained models achieved respectively 98.2%, 98.4% and 98.5% of accuracy on the test set.

(a) Piece disassembly scenario

(b) LEGO[®] assembly scenario

(c) Tower of Hanoi scenario

Fig. 1: The three validation scenarios

A. Human-Robot Collaboration Scenarios

The same scenarios have been made collaborative to assess how the IPM behaves in HRC settings, introducing a collaborative robot to the equation. In this case, each scenario involves a human operator H and a cobot C , and similarly to the before-mentioned methodology, H and C operate within a discrete state environment. Both entities are enabled to perform a set of tasks, denoted respectively as I_H and I_C . With no loss of generality, it is possible to assume that some tasks may fall outside the scope of I , i.e., $I \subseteq (I_H \cup I_C)$. In particular, tasks $i_H, i_C \notin I$ are preparatory or background activities that do not modify $Conf$ when executed, i.e.,

$$T(Conf_t, i_e) = Conf_t \quad \forall i_e \in I_H \cup I_C \wedge i_e \notin I$$

Consequently, such tasks are not considered by the IPM.

The collaborative scenarios are characterized as follows:

- *Piece disassembly*: the human and cobot work simultaneously to unscrew a plastic piece. The system predicts the human's next selected screw and assigns the cobot a compatible one to optimize workflow, reduce task completion time, and prevent collisions. The human also removes processed screws and unscrewed plastic layers.
- *LEGO[®] assembly*: the cobot delivers pieces from a warehouse while the human assembles them into a forklift component. The system predicts the next required piece to support the procedure. Here, the cobot performs preparatory tasks, while the human assembles the components after receiving the pieces.
- *Tower of Hanoi*: both the human and cobot perform game moves (i.e. the tasks) in a sequential, turn-based manner, with the cobot anticipating human moves and adhering to specific game rules. This scenario aims to reduce execution time and enhance collaboration through shared decision-making.

Specifically, the three collaborative scenarios were designed with distinct task assignment logics to account for and manage the intricacies of each context. Additionally,

TABLE IV: Overview of scenarios characteristics

Scenario	Collaboration modality	Task intersection
Piece disassembly	Simultaneous	$I_H \setminus I \neq \emptyset, \quad I_C \cap I = I_C$
LEGO [®] assembly	Supportive	$I_H \cap I = I_H, \quad I_C \cap I = \emptyset$
Tower-of Hanoi	Sequential	$I_H \cup I_C = I$

they incorporate different collaboration modalities [22] and task intersections (i.e., tasks the entities are enabled to perform), as detailed in Table IV. This setup was used to test and validate the model's adaptability across different HRC scenarios while maintaining a consistent structure, demonstrating its effectiveness in diverse use cases with varying characteristics. A demo video is available¹.

B. The Experimental Setup

The setup features a collaborative workspace. Participants are seated in front of the scenario station, facing the cobots. A UR5e is used for the Piece disassembly scenario, and the ABB GoFa CRB 15000 is used for the other two. In the LEGO[®] assembly scenario, the ABB GoFa can autonomously switch tools during execution. A Vision System with a RealSense D455/D435 camera monitors each scenario workspace. Cobot controllers are housed beneath the workbench, communicating with the orchestration system via socket communication. All experiments were conducted on a high-performance workstation featuring an Intel Core i7-13700 KF processor, 64 GB of RAM, and an NVIDIA RTX 4070 TI GPU, which also handled the training and execution of all AI models.

C. The System's Architecture

The IPM has been integrated into an orchestration system, which architecture is depicted in Fig. 2. The orchestration system includes several components responsible for different

¹<https://youtu.be/IRW61k7FdGc>

Fig. 2: Orchestration system architecture

functionalities. The IPM is fed by a Vision System, which integrates object recognition models. The predictions are delivered to a Task Assignment Module, which instructs the Cobot Agent based on a specific logic. Finally, the system’s reasoning and processing are visualized in a Dashboard, exemplified in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Snapshot of the Piece disassembly scenario Dashboard, showing the detected dynamic human features, the configuration of the scenario (the screws status) captured by the Vision System’s AI modules along with the IPM’s output (the white square, close to the hand-screw) and the cobot speed (top left corner)

D. Task Assignment Logic

Due to significant differences in structure, objectives, and collaboration methods across scenarios, distinct task assignment strategies were implemented to manage scenario execution. This approach contributed to the evaluation of the IPM using various task assignment logics, further assessing its generalizability across different contexts. Consequently, three dedicated task assignment logics were developed.

These logics take as input i_H , the human task, and aim to determine the next i_C , the cobot task. Note that i_H is provided both by the IPM, i.e., the predicted human task (denoted as i_H^*), and by the Vision System, i.e., the detected human task (denoted as \hat{i}_H). In fact, the orchestration system uses prediction not as the sole basis for decision-making but as a guiding mechanism complemented by scenario-specific fallback strategies and feedback management. This ensures the system can accurately account for the operator’s intentions and adapt to unexpected or exceptional situations.

1) **Piece disassembly scenario:** the assignment logic determines the next task i_C for the cobot based on human operator’s behaviour. Specifically, if H is processing a screw, the Vision System is able to detect it and provide \hat{i}_H that will be considered for the C task assignment, otherwise i_H^* provided by IPM is used. More formally:

$$i_H = \begin{cases} \hat{i}_H, & \text{if available (detected)} \\ i_H^*, & \text{otherwise (predicted)} \end{cases}$$

Predicting i_H^* is useful because often \hat{i}_H is not detected, either due to occlusions in the scene or because the human is performing other activities instead of unscrewing. Even when the operator is performing an unscrewing operation, the processing time is very fast. Consequently, if the cobot would have to wait for a valid \hat{i}_H it would spend much time idling. Instead, by predicting the unscrewing task that the human is more likely to perform (i_H), the system is able to immediately determine i_C , by assigning C a complementary task based on a distance-minimization criteria (e.g., by selecting the farthest screw).

Specifically, given the spatial position of the scenario element involved in the task i_H , which is the position of the screw involved in the human unscrewing task denoted as $P(i_H)$, the orchestration system selects i_C using a distance-based approach: the farthest processable screw (i.e., among screwed ones) is prioritized. Let $Conf_A$ be the set of available screws: $Conf_A = \{n | n = \text{available}, n \notin Conf_H\}$, where $Conf_H$ denotes screws close to H that are restricted for processing by C . The selected screw n^* is:

$$n^* = \underset{n \in Conf_A}{\operatorname{argmax}} D(P(i_H), P(n))$$

where $P(n)$ is the position of the n -th screw and $D(P(i_H), P(n))$ is the Euclidean distance between the screw processed by the human and the n -th screw. If no screws are available ($Conf_A = \emptyset$), C remains at its home position and waits. The main task execution constraints are that screws close to the hand-screw are excluded from $Conf_A$ to avoid interference and that C does not process screws in $Conf_H$ unless H remains inactive for at least 15 seconds:

$$I_C = \begin{cases} I \setminus I \cap I_H, & t_{idle}(H) < 15s \\ I \cap I_H, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where $t_{idle}(H)$ is H ’s inactivity time.

If neither the Vision System nor the IPM provide a compatible i , the first available screw from $Conf_A$ is selected as a fallback task i_C for C .

2) **LEGO® assembly scenario**: the assignment logic determines which LEGO® pieces the cobot C should bring to the human operator H , so that they can be assembled. The idea in this scenario is that predicting the human task i_H enables to follow diverse and personalized assembly sequences by dynamically selecting diverse i_C , rather than having the same pattern for each operator or to model all the possible sequences.

Consequently, the selection process follows a simple principle: the initial selection of the piece to be withdrawn from the warehouse is always performed by H . Subsequently, pieces are delivered based on the IPM’s suggestion, i.e., the predicted task i_H^* . H may accept the provided piece by confirming through a gesture. If the delivered piece is incorrect or undesired, H points towards the correct piece located in the warehouse area, denoted as \hat{i}_H . The system orchestrator recognises the indicated piece and instructs the robot accordingly.

i_H represents the current assembly task performed by the human operator H . If H confirms and assembles the provided piece, it means that the predicted next task matches the actual one, formally defined as: $i_H^* = i_H$. However, if H manually selects a different piece, the prediction deviates from the actual task, and thus: $i_H^* \neq i_H$, $\hat{i}_H = i_H$

3) **Tower of Hanoi scenario**: the assignment logic determines which action the cobot C should perform. It can execute two types of actions: approach (α), positioning itself near the rod from which it will pick up a disk for the next move, and the effective move (i_C), picking up a disk from one rod and placing it onto another. The idea is to reduce game completion times, by preparing C in advance based on the move i_H that H is more likely to perform. To this purpose, the approach action is determined based on the IPM’s suggestion, which predicts H ’s next move i_H^* . While the human is still performing the move, C preemptively approaches the rod from which it should perform its next move, assuming that the move i_H^* will be performed, ensuring readiness for i_C . More formally:

$$\alpha(t) = A(Conf(t), i_H^*)$$

where the function A represents the game state transition function assuming H follows the predicted move i_H^* on a specific game configuration $Conf$. In such case, C is already in the correct position to execute its move. Otherwise, C recalculates the optimal move based on the actual game configuration detected through the Vision System:

$$\alpha(t) = A(Conf(t), \hat{i}_H)$$

Then, the cobot is able to start its turn and perform the move i_C , computed through the optimal resolution strategy, given the updated configuration after H ’s move.

V. RESULTS

The validation phase had a dual focus: first, independently validating the IPM in the three manufacturing scenarios, and second, evaluating the entire orchestration system in collaborative setups. Both validations utilized the defined

scenarios—the former assessing quantitative metrics based on individual human task execution, while the latter focused also on qualitative collaboration metrics.

A. IPM performance in Individual Scenarios

Similarly to the training, the validation involved three participants with different level of expertise with the task (newbie, regular and expert), performing a fixed number of rounds per each scenario. Results are reported in Table V.

TABLE V: Overview of IPM validation performance

Scenario	# of predictions	Accuracy
Piece disassembly	225	83.1%
LEGO® assembly	406	77.6%
Tower-of Hanoi	347	89.9%

The model’s validation showed a performance gap compared to training, where accuracy exceeded 98% for each scenario. This is likely due to differences in participant behavior compared to the training data, which had limited generalization due to the small number of subjects.

Despite this, the model correctly predicted human intentions in most cases. Lower accuracy in scenarios like Piece disassembly and LEGO® assembly is acceptable, as multiple valid task sequences exist, requiring the model to choose among several possibilities at each step.

Additionally, analysis of the confusion matrices provided key insights: even when predictions were incorrect, the suggested task was often spatially or logically close to the one chosen by the human. This highlights the potential of partial intention recognition—having a general but not fully precise understanding of human actions or interaction areas can still offer valuable insights. This capability is further assessed by validating the model in a collaborative setup.

B. Insights from the Collaborative Scenarios

The validation experiments on the collaborative setup involved 12 volunteers. While most had prior experience with cobots, only two had previously interacted with these specific scenarios. Consequently, the majority were considered inexperienced in this context and relied heavily on the system to complete the tasks. Each participant first performed an individual preliminary execution to familiarize themselves with the scenario. The second execution served as a baseline for comparing individual performance with the third, collaborative execution. This process was repeated across all three scenarios.

The collaborative validation phase showed varying intention prediction accuracies across the scenarios: 49% for Piece disassembly, 94.2% for LEGO® assembly, and 82.5% for the Tower of Hanoi. This performance gap with respect to both model training and individual validation can be attributed to several key factors. The main reason is the introduction of a cobot created unfamiliar scenario configurations that were not part of the original training data, which was designed to predict human moves in isolation, especially in the Piece disassembly scenario where entities modify the $Conf$ vector

simultaneously. Additionally, while training data benefited from careful manual labeling, real-time predictions relied on Vision Systems that could introduce errors in status detection, leading to configuration inconsistencies.

Despite the lower accuracies, the IPM was effectively able to understand human intention in most cases, allowing cobots to dynamically complement participants actions. Interestingly, the LEGO® assembly had better accuracy compared to the individual validation, but that’s probably due to the fact that inexperienced participants which were not sure about the assembly sequence tent to accept the provided piece regardless of their actual intention.

In addition to prediction accuracy, the validation focused on user-side metrics to assess the performance of the orchestration system. These metrics were collected through a post-execution questionnaire evaluating participants’ perceptions of interacting with the cobot in each scenario. The average values of the collected metrics are presented in Table VI. This qualitative evaluation provided key insights into the effectiveness of the overall system, which played a crucial role in shaping the interaction, human decision-making and task execution, though its impact varied across scenarios.

In the Piece disassembly scenario, the system’s adaptability proved beneficial despite low prediction accuracy. Since incorrect predictions rarely caused inefficiencies—the cobot could safely unscrew a different screw even if closer to the operator—task execution remained smooth. Participants perceived the interaction as fluid, demonstrating that even partial intention recognition effectively supported task progression.

In the LEGO® assembly scenario, high prediction accuracy enabled the cobot to anticipate and provide the next piece efficiently. However, the collaboration was affected by automation inefficiencies, requiring better synchronization. Despite this, participants valued the proactive assistance of the cobot which facilitated task execution, particularly for those who were inexperienced and uncertain about the assembly sequence.

TABLE VI: Average values of qualitative metrics, for each scenario (values in range 0-100, the higher the better)

Metric	Piece	LEGO®	Tower
Collaborative experience: how would you rate your collaboration with the cobot?	67.5	57.5	87.9
Collaboration importance: did you find working with a cobot that predicts your movements and adapts its strategy more useful than working individually?	69.5	50.4	89.1
Prediction effectiveness: how effective did you find the cobot to predict your intention and act accordingly?	65.0	70.0	84.5
Cobot trust: how did you trust the cobot during the experiment?	64.1	66.2	80.0
Task allocation: how did you find the task allocation management, were cobot’s tasks efficiently allocated?	76.6	69.5	89.1
Task coordination: did you find it easy to coordinate with the cobot?	68.3	66.6	88.3
Task enjoyment: how enjoyable was the task with respect to the individual modality?	71.6	65.5	81.2

In the Tower of Hanoi scenario, the collaboration was particularly effective, with accurate predictions enabling the cobot to anticipate movements and seamlessly complement participants’ actions. The well-structured interaction provided an engaging and satisfying experience, with the cobot actively supporting players’ strategies and assisting inexperienced participants. Overall, the orchestration system improved efficiency and user experience by adapting to varying task demands, optimizing workflow in structured tasks and ensuring adaptability in more variable scenarios.

1) *Task assignment effectiveness:* Although the IPM serves as a core component of the task assignment logic, its role varies across different scenarios and is not always the primary decision driver. The orchestration system demonstrates adaptability by using predictions selectively: only when vision detection fails in the first scenario, allowing human override in LEGO® piece selection in the second scenario, and adapting to actual human moves in the game. This is mostly evident in the Piece disassembly scenario, which demonstrated substantially lower accuracy compared to other implementations. Despite of that, dynamic task reallocation effectively handled variability, highlighting the value of partial intention recognition. In fact, experimental results show that the task assignment logic maintains its effectiveness even when predictions are less accurate, successfully determining appropriate cobot moves and maintaining consistent task allocation across different collaboration modes. This multi-layered approach ensures system reliability by not solely depending on predictions but rather incorporating them into a broader decision-making framework that can adapt to actual human actions and preferences.

The main limitation of this approach lies in the need for a custom task assignment logic for each collaborative scenario. A possible solution is to extend the framework proposed in [23], which dynamically prioritizes tasks based on the current scenario state and configuration, by integrating the use of human intention prediction. Alternatively, the solution presented in [24], which enables personalized task allocation and dynamic synthesis of optimized collaborative plans without relying on predefined static behaviours, offers another promising direction. Incorporating such approaches would enhance the system’s generality in task allocation and will be a key focus for future developments.

2) *Collaboration safety and smoothness analysis:* The experimental results demonstrated positive coordination outcomes with no collisions or dangerous situations, particularly noteworthy in the Piece disassembly scenario, where human and robot worked together in close proximity, though this may be partially attributed to operators’ natural tendency to maintain safe distances. However, while the IPM and task assignment logic were consistently integrated despite occasional errors and inefficiencies, the automation components (i.e., the cobot behaviour) presented significant challenges. The Tower of Hanoi scenario proved to be the most stable with precise cobot movements, but the other scenarios encountered some operational issues: the Piece disassembly scenario suffered from stuck screws and failed unscrewing

attempts, while the LEGO® assembly scenario struggled with inefficient tool changes and inaccurate piece retrieval. These automation challenges, though not the main focus of the research, require substantial improvements alongside additional coordination mechanisms to ensure a smooth and satisfying collaboration experience.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This study advances HRC in manufacturing by developing a general methodology for predicting human intentions across various scenarios, enabling dynamic cobot task adaptation. The methodology was applied to three use cases: Piece disassembly, LEGO® assembly, and the Tower of Hanoi game. The model performed well in individual scenario evaluations, with satisfactory intention prediction accuracy, before being integrated into a collaborative orchestration system for real-world validation.

Tested with 12 participants, the system showed adaptability across diverse HRC contexts, demonstrating effective task adaptation and collaboration support, despite lower intention prediction accuracy. Discrepancies in real-world performance were attributed to limited data generalization and environmental variability. Nevertheless, the task assignment logic proved resilient, ensuring smooth collaboration by integrating fallback mechanisms and human feedback. While the system achieved strong coordination outcomes with no reported collisions, some automation inefficiencies impacted performance in certain scenarios. Specifically, the system improved efficiency and role synchronization in the Tower of Hanoi scenario and handled task variability in the Piece disassembly use case, despite moderate accuracy. However, inefficiencies emerged in the LEGO® assembly, pointing to the need for improved automation strategies.

Future work will focus on enhancing cobot adaptability by integrating human factors, task performance metrics, and emotional and behavioural responses to improve contextual awareness. Additionally, refining task assignment logic and boosting automation reliability, along with addressing explainability concerns, will enhance the system's capabilities and broaden its support for industrial HRC applications.

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